

Recommended citation: Pelz, M., Lang, M., Ozmen, Y., Schröder, J., Walker, F., & Müller, R. (2018). The possibility of improving individual learning processes by a digital preliminary and introductory phase for civil engineering students. In Clark, R., Munkebo Hussmann, P., Järvinen, H.-M., Murphy, M., & Etchells Vigild, M. (Eds.), *Creativity, Innovation and Entrepreneurship for Engineering Education Excellence. SEFI 46th Annual Conference* (pp. 1118-1124). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Brussels, Belgium. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14672804.

The possibility of improving individual learning processes by a digital preliminary and introductory phase for civil engineering students

M. Pelz

Doctoral candidate

Technology and Didactics of Technology, University of Duisburg-Essen
Essen, Germany

E-mail: marcel.pelz@uni-due.de

M. Lang

Professor

Technology and Didactics of Technology, University of Duisburg-Essen
Essen, Germany

E-mail: m.lang@uni-due.de

Y. Özmen

Doctoral candidate

Institute of Mechanics, University of Duisburg-Essen
Essen, Germany

E-mail: yasemin.oezmen@uni-due.de

J. Schröder

Professor

Institute of Mechanics, University of Duisburg-Essen
Essen, Germany

E-mail: j.schroeder@uni-due.de

F. Walker

Junior Professor

Didactics of Technology, Technical University of Kaiserslautern
Kaiserslautern, Germany

E-mail: walker@mv.uni-kl.de

R. Müller

Professor

Chair for Applied Mechanics, Technical University of Kaiserslautern
Kaiserslautern, Germany

E-mail: ram@rhrk.uni-kl.de

INTRODUCTION

The German higher education landscape is dealing with the problem of dropping out of university without a degree for years [cf. 1,2]. Decisive for discussing this topic are the high numbers of university dropouts. For example, a recent study by the DZHW (German Center for Higher Education Research and Science Studies) shows that one in three undergraduates drop out of university without a degree in engineering (reference group: first-year students studying a Bachelor's degree at universities in 2010/2011) [1]. In a focused examination of the field of civil engineering, actually a drop out of the studies can be observed in 48% of the first-year students [1]. Other studies refer to similar figures on the European scale [2,3].

First of all students complete a complex drop out process before the final decision on disenrollment is made [1]. Besides the fitting problems regarding students' interest and study requirements, performance problems - especially in basic subjects (such as engineering mechanics (EM) or engineering mathematics) - are to be seen as a decisive factor within the various phases of this process [4]. A deepened examination of the performance problems point out that the critical motives are final failures in exams, a perception of too high study requirements or even self-doubts regarding the own suitability of the named subject [1]. Several studies [i.a. 5,6] justify the mentioned performance problems with a decrease of special expertise and mathematical knowledge among first-year students. However, in the introductory phase of the studies, there is not enough time to work on these knowledge gaps [7].

In general, the introductory phase in engineering courses can be attributed a central importance for the further success of the students during their studies. Figures show that already in the first semester, 42% of the drop-outs disenroll, in the following semester there are another 31% [1]. Henn & Polaczek [5] could already prove that students without study success in their first semester, describe the largest share of disenrollment at universities. Therefore, a direct connection between lack of study success in the introductory phase and the early termination of the studies can be constructed.

1 REFERENCE MODEL FOR QUALITY ASSURANCE

Heublein & In der Smitten [6] have adopted this problem and developed a reference model for quality assurance at faculties of engineering sciences. The reference model states that a variety of supportive measures at different times throughout the course of the studies can be helpful and improve the students success. Preventative measures can be used both in the preliminary phase (self-assessments and prep courses) and in the introductory phase (additional learning offers) (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Reference model for quality assurance in the course of the studies (own representation in dependence on Heublein & In der Smitten [6])

Almost all universities are offering similar support measures for a long time, with the objective of making it easier for new students to begin their studies. However, the above mentioned offers are not very well received by the prospective and first-year students, further consideration of those who are absent indicate that these are mainly those who urgently need such assistance or offers [1]. So far, the question remains unclear whether such measures in general can cause any improvement or the type of content is inappropriate.

Approaches that embed these support measures into an online environment already exist. However, at present available online offers of the mentioned support measures (e.g. Studicheck¹, OMB+² or MathBridge³) only provide a few and mostly subject-unspecific topics. Engineering application contexts, such as the EM, remain completely untreated. So far, there are no relevant empirical findings regarding the effectiveness of such support measures.

As a result of the stated, the collaborative research project FUNDAMENT deals with this topic, the basic project idea is explained in the following section.

2 THE COLLABORATIVE RESEARCH PROJECT FUNDAMENT

The support of individual learning processes in civil engineering studies by the use of digital higher education is the objective of the collaborative research project “Förderung des individuellen Lernerfolgs mittels digitaler Medien im Bauingenieurstudium” – FUNDAMENT (Improvement of individual learning success by the use of digital media in civil engineering). The collaboration of the University of Duisburg-Essen (UDE) and the Technical University of Kaiserslautern has developed a support concept that intervenes preventively in the preliminary and the introductory phase (Fig. 1). The support concept includes an online self-assessment (OSA) and an online prep course (OPC) in the preliminary phase; in the introductory phase additional learning opportunities are offered in the form of interactive online modules (IOM).

By using the OSA, an active engagement with their own interests and their fit to the content and framework conditions of the study program should be encouraged for the

¹ <https://studicheck.nrw>, accessed April 25th, 2018

² <https://www.ombplus.de>, accessed April 25th, 2018

³ <http://www.math-bridge.org>, accessed April 25th, 2018

prospective students. A feedback regarding the fitting of the own previous knowledge with the knowledge requirements of the favoured study course is also offered. The composition of the OSA is divided into two parts: first the determinants of the PPIK-model according to Ackerman [8] (vocational interest, intellectual commitment, crystalline and fluid intelligence) are tested using suitable instruments, while the second part focuses on previous knowledge. In addition to the mathematical basics (MB), which are relevant for civil engineering studies, natural science basics (NB) are retrieved. The NB are the fundamentals of physics needed in engineering mechanics. Prospective students will receive personalized feedback after completing the OSA, indicating gaps in previous knowledge. The implementation of the OSA took place in a moodle⁴-environment in combination with JACK⁵.

Downstream of the OSA an OPC is offered, which should serve to close the previously uncovered knowledge gaps. An OPC is an online prep course, also known as a bridging course, which normally starts a few weeks before the beginning of the studies with the objective of improving or deepening the school knowledge. As in the case of the OSA, there are hardly any empirical findings in terms of effectiveness, also the number of users is just about half of the prospective students [9]. The content areas are identical to those of the OSA (MB and NB). The OPC is based on the principle of learning by example [10] with informative tutorial feedback [11] embedded in an engineering context. The implementation also takes place in a moodle-environment in combination with JACK. JACK is a server-based system for executing computer-based tests with automatic feedback generation. Especially for exercises within the OPC, features such as parameterization, staged hints can be used as support and a detailed feedback evaluation.

Prusty et al. [12] discovered in a study of the introductory phase that new students have difficulties in understanding the key core concepts. So-called IOM could be helpful regarding this problem. Within FUNDAMENT, the IOM are understood as a "3-pillar concept", which is used in the EM1 and EM2 courses. The three pillars are learning videos (experimental videos to illustrate the core concepts and animated slideshows as teaching and learning support for calculating exercises), JACK exercises and online communication. Last-mentioned should strengthen the integration into the academic community. This is another major problem especially for programs with large numbers of new students and should also be regarded as a factor for the dropout [1].

3 METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

The classic experimental and control group design is used to examine the effectiveness of the entire support strategy and the support measures (OSA, OPC and IOM) on their own. The students attending the EM1 (1st semester) or EM2 (2nd semester) courses in the previous conceptual design are assigned to the control group. If they use the integrated IOM in the mentioned courses, they are assigned to the study group (Fig. 2).

⁴ <https://moodle.org>, accessed April 25th, 2018

⁵ <http://s3.uni-duisburg-essen.de/jack>, accessed April 25th, 2018

Fig. 2. Longitudinal design of the collaborative research project FUNDAMENT
(© Technology and Didactics of Technology – UDE)

The three online elements and the test instruments will be piloted from the winter term 2017/2018 up to and including the summer term 2018. Afterwards the data of the main study will be collected starting in the winter term 2018/2019 until the end of the summer term 2019. Both in the pilot phase and in the main study, the longitudinal collection of data takes place at four measurement points (MP) (Fig. 2).

With the help of the results achieved at the MP in the applied tests about engineering mechanics (EM, calculating ability and mathematical modelling ability) according to Dammann & Lang [13], the grade and the achieved credits, the effect of the support strategy is examined. Referring to the PPIK-theory, the construct of vocational interest is collected using the General Interest Structure Test (Allgemeiner Interessen-Struktur-Test – Revision AIST-R) along with the Environmental Structure Test (Umwelt-Struktur-Test – Revision UST-R) according to Bergmann & Eder [14].

The Typical Intellectual Engagement (TIE) is determined by a German-language questionnaire according to Wilhelm et al. [15]. Basic cognitive abilities are assessed

by using the Culture Fair Intelligence Test (Grundintelligenztest Skala 2 – Revision CFT 20-R) according to Weiß [16]. In addition, demographic data, but also information regarding the school career are collected.

4 OUTLOOK

The final stage of the pilot phase has begun at both locations. The online elements will be examined regarding their effectiveness on the basis of the collected data. Likewise, the data will be used to allow a revision of the elements in terms of the main study.

First evaluations of the individual MP indicate a low number of test persons. On a closer inspection of continuous data sets, over the previously collected data of MP1-3, only numbers in the single-digit range can be achieved. Despite an advertised test person compensation of 100 euro for the complete finalization of all four MP, a high drop-out can be assumed. This situation, which is unacceptable in consideration of the main study, is currently being analysed more closely and different approaches are discussed. For example, a readjustment of the survey to a paper & pencil-test would be conceivable, as well as an award of bonus points for the EM-exam.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Special thanks go to the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) for funding the collaborative research project FUNDAMENT (FKZ 16DHL1024 and 16DHL1025) within the framework of the guideline for the promotion of “Research on digital higher education” within the first funding line.

REFERENCES

- [1] Heublein, U., Ebert, J., Isleib, S., Hutzsch, C., König, R., Richter, J. et al. (2017), Zwischen Studienerwartungen und Studienwirklichkeit - Ursachen des Studienabbruchs, beruflicher Verbleib der Studienabbrecherinnen und Studienabbrecher und Entwicklung der Studienabbruchquote an deutschen Hochschulen, Deutsches Zentrum für Hochschul- und Wissenschaftsforschung GmbH, Hannover.
- [2] Pinxten, M., De Laet, T., Van Soom, C., Peeters, C., Kautz, C., Hockicko, P., et al. (2017), Approaches to the Identification of STEM Key Competencies in European University systems, Proceedings of the 45th Annual SEFI Conference 2017, 389–397.
- [3] De Laet, T., Broos, T., Van Staalduinen, J.-P., Ebner, M., Langie, G., Van Soom, C. et al. (2017), Confidence in and Beliefs about First-year Engineering Student Success - Case Study from KU Leuven, TU Delft, and TU Graz, Proceedings of the 45th SEFI Conference 2017, 894–902.
- [4] Heublein, U., Hutzsch, C., Schreiber, S., Sommer, D. and Besuch, G. (2009), Ursachen des Studienabbruchs in Bachelor- und in herkömmlichen Studiengängen - Ergebnisse einer bundesweiten Befragung von Exmatrikulierten des Studienjahres 2007/08, Deutsches Zentrum für Hochschul- und Wissenschaftsforschung GmbH, Hannover.
- [5] Henn, G. and Polaczek, C. (2007), Studienerfolg in den Ingenieurwissenschaften, Das Hochschulwesen - Forum Für Hochschulforschung, -Praxis Und -Politik, 144–7.
- [6] Heublein, U. and In der Smitten, S. (2013), Referenzmodell zur Qualitätssicherung an

- Fachbereichen und Fakultäten des Maschinenbaus und der Elektrotechnik - Konzept für die Lehre. HIS-Institut für Hochschulforschung, Hannover.
- [7] Willige, J., Woisch, A., Grützmaker, J. and Naumann, H. (2014), Studienqualitätsmonitor SQM 2014 - Online-Befragung Studierender im Sommersemester 2014 (Fächergruppen an Universitäten), Deutsches Zentrum für Hochschul- und Wissenschaftsforschung GmbH, Hannover.
- [8] Ackerman, P.L. (1996), A theory of adult intellectual development - Process, personality, interests, and knowledge, *Intelligence*, No. 22, 227–57.
- [9] Grützmaker, J. and Willige, J. (2016), Die Studieneingangsphase aus Studierendensicht - Ergebnisse aus dem Studienqualitätsmonitor 2015, Deutsches Zentrum für Hochschul- und Wissenschaftsforschung GmbH, Hannover.
- [10] Schworm, S. (2004), Lernen aus Beispielen - computerbasierte Lernumgebungen zum Erwerb argumentativer und didaktischer Fertigkeiten, Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg i.Br.
- [11] Narciss, S. (2006), Informatives tutorielles Feedback: Entwicklungs- und Evaluationsprinzipien auf der Basis instruktionspsychologischer Erkenntnisse, Waxmann, Münster.
- [12] Prusty, B.G., Ho, O. and Ho, S. (2009), Adaptive tutorials using eLearning platform for solid mechanics course in engineering, 20th Annual Conference for the Australasian Association for Engineering Education, *Engineering the Curriculum*, 828.
- [13] Dammann, E. and Lang, M. (in print), Mechanisch-mathematisches Modellieren als Prädiktor für Studienerfolg in der Eingangsphase des Bauingenieurstudiums, Tagungsband der 12 Ingenieurpädagogischen Regionaltagung an der TU Ilmenau, Ilmenau.
- [14] Bergmann, C. and Eder, F. (2005), Allgemeiner Interessen-Struktur-Test (AIST-R) mit Umwelt-Struktur-Test (UST-R) - Revision, Beltz Test GmbH, Göttingen.
- [15] Wilhelm, O., Schulze, R., Schmiedek, F. and Süß, H.-M. (2003), Interindividuelle Unterschiede im typischen intellektuellen Engagement, *Diagnostica*, 49, 49–60.
- [16] Weiß, R.H. (2006), Grundintelligenztest Skala 2 - Revision (CFT 20-R), Hogrefe, Göttingen.